

Proactive personality literature through scientometric analysis

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2022, 15(02), 177–185

Publication history: Received on 03 July 2022; revised on 06 August 2022; accepted on 08 August 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2022.15.2.0802>

Abstract

The proactive personality is designed to seize a behavioral tendency to impose, or change, a person's environment. This take a look at goals to observe the popularity and role of the visible maps of global studies and the Scopus listed proactive character literature the usage of bibliometric positioning images. The studies turned into carried out the usage of a bibliometric technique. Data evaluation and use of the VOSViewer visualization application and the Scopus characteristic to examine seek results. In this review, the information amassed follow to 496 files posted from 1993 to 2020. The take a look at famous that Renmin University of China and United State is the maximum energetic affiliated and country institutions, scientists and countries within side the proactive character literature. In the proactive character literature, Business, Management and Accounting and Journal of Vocational Behavior are the maximum studied fields and reasserts of dissemination. There is one map of businesses round the arena with collaborative researchers. To discover the frame of expertise produced from thirty- years of publication, this take a look at constructs a convergence axis grouping inclusive of proactive character literature: Personality, Employee, Career, Organization, Manager, and Entrepreneur, abbreviated as PECOME.

Keywords: Career; Education; Organization; Proactive personality

1. Introduction

Personality, that's described as a surprisingly solid tendency to persuade environmental changes, refers to a dispositional tendency to have interaction in proactive behavior in a number of situations. Behavioral rationale is concept to be crucial for knowledge how humans have interaction in an activity, and Theory of Planned Behavior via way of means of Ajzen in [1] indicates that the aim is decided with the aid of using 3 factors: mindset towards behavior, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control. Individuals with proactive character generally tend to extrude situations on purpose, inclusive of their bodily environment [2]. At a general level, persona is described as a dispositional tendency to take private initiative in diverse activities and situations [3]. Proactive persona captures a behavioral tendency to impose, or change, a person's environment. The proactive persona prototype is defined as 'a person who's quite unchanged with the aid of using situational forces, and who affects environmental change [4] such as high creativity in exploiting market niches [5] which plays an important role [6] persona associated with some of proactive profession outcomes, inclusive of salary, promoting and profession satisfaction, at the attributes of charismatic leadership [7] so as to achieve competitive advantage [8]. The proactive persona identifies possibilities and acts on them; they display initiative, take action, and bear till it produces significant change [9]. Traits and behaviors that mirror the complementary inclinations and moves achieved with the aid of using people with the intention of shaping themselves and their environment [10]. Today's offices are noting a shift from conventional structural and engineering carrier work to modes that rely heavily on team-based, short and challenging work; personnel want to be impartial and use initiative to work successfully in this environment [11]. To cope with the aggressive environment that drives the dynamics, companies are now no longer working hard, but are also showing a more personal initiative in

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fixing problems and looking for possibilities for improvement. Indeed, many argue that organizational income and fulfilment depend on personal initiative and proactive behavior [4]. Information exchange enhances creativity because it provides cognitive resources for creativity [12], consistently being ranked as the primary ability sought by way of employers [13].

The resulting economic and organizational changes dramatically affect individual job and career settings in terms of increased flexibility, vulnerability, uncertainty, and non-linearity [14]. Organizations an increasing number of anticipate personnel to accurate matters they see as wrong, act at the facts they have, and react to uncommon instances with the aid of using showing proactive behavior. Proactive character is one of the drivers of proactive behavior within side the workplace. Employees with proactive personalities take initiative, are persistent, and are trying to find to form their environment. A proactive character can advantage one's profession in phrases of performance, process adjustment, and extrinsic and intrinsic profession success [15]. Career self-control characterizes character personnel as unfastened agents who have to be proactive in searching for and taking part in training and growing possibilities to maintain inner and outside marketing [16]. At the Centre of organizational access is the newcomer's idea of adjustment, which combines the knowledge, confidence, and motivation to take on a job role, and dedication to the company and its goals. [17]. Employee initiative and proactiveness are vital drivers of organizational effectiveness [18] which can influence career success [19]. Organizations need high-skilled employees who are willing and able to work in a wider range of roles [20] in order to minimize dependence on work [21]. The job may be seen as a particular form of proactive behavior: the job begins to develop in and of itself and specializes in how personnel understand their work environment and act according to their personal preferences, values and skills [22], such as skills, competencies, abilities, education, and experiences [23], [24]. Employees can engage in proactive activities as part of their role behavior for which they meet basic job requirements [25] for advancement and excellent management skills [26].

Positive organizational, such as sales performance, entrepreneurial behavior, individual innovation, and small company innovation [27]. It is consequently vital to increase a higher information of the manner through which proactive people obtain better ranges of profession success [28]. The exceptionally proactive persona strives to enhance the cutting-edge scenario and apprehend possibilities and comply with through, display initiative, take action, and persist till significant modifications occur [29]. In a study conducted by [30] confirmed that proactive character probably moderates the wonderful outcomes of organizational profession increase possibilities on person profession outcomes, in order that the blessings of organizational profession increase are probably to be maximum useful for tremendously proactive individuals. In general, preceding studies associated with proactive character has simplest tested one studies topic, which includes one country [31] and one field [32]. Unfortunately, even though its presentations great photograph maps visualized from year to year with information from numerous posted researches on a worldwide scale, there isn't a lot literature on proactive character. The strong positive relationship concerning affiliation, scholars, and the effect of scientific research has additionally now no longer been explicitly mentioned with the aid of using any publication. This take a look at objectives to take a look at the location of literature within side the subject of proactive character with the aid of using researchers at the worldwide stage posted the world over listed with the aid of using Scopus the use of bibliometric positions. We monitored the boom within side the range of scientific files associated with proactive character posted and listed with the aid of using Scopus from 1993 to 2020.

2. Material and methods

This evaluation maps the status of research finished within side the final 36 years at a worldwide degree primarily based totally on "Proactive Personality". In January 2021, this observe accumulated statistics from Scopus the usage of a record seek query. The maximum regularly mentioned studies subjects had been derived from the abstracts of Scopus articles that had been tested the usage of content material analysis [33]. The look at become performed the use of bibliometric techniques. To examine seek results, use the VOS Viewer application and the Scopus characteristic to examine data [34].

This look at identifies proactive character key phrases to discover and seek courses within side Scopus database of 496 files published worldwide from 1993 to 2020. This view limits the record series to the year 2020 and excludes the year 2021. Grade records from January through December are collected to replicate the public's view of the direction of the year. TITLE ABS ("Proactive Personality") KEY AND PUBYEAR <2021 is an enter question command this is applied whilst mining educational eBook records within side the Scopus on-line database.

This observe applies authorship evaluation collectively with writer evaluation unit and complete calculation systematic approach the usage of VOSViewer to reap studies community of worldwide collaborative researchers. This observe plays an in-intensity co-occasion evaluation with key-word relationship evaluation and a completely systematic computation approach the usage of VOSViewer to generate a key-word map community.

3. Results and discussion

The proactive personality literature seems to generally tend to boom and develop with every passing year. The maximum factor for global guide is 97 files in 2020. Since 1993, publishing on proactive character has started.

3.1. Proactive Personality Literature Most Common Organizational Affiliations

Major research institutes in the field of proactive personality are 12 documents at Renmin University of China, followed by 10 documents at Peking University, 10 documents at Notre Dame University, 10 documents at Shanghai Jiao Tong University, 9 documents at Mississippi State University, Louisiana Institute of Technology. 8 Universities, 8 Portland State Universities, 7 Florida Universities, 7 City of Hongkong Universities.

Source: Scopus data base

Figure 1 Organizational Affiliation Number of Annual Publication of Proactive Personality Literature

3.2. Proactive Personality Literature Most Individual Researcher

The most authored researcher in the field of proactive personality is Crant, J.M. with 11 documents, followed by Bakker, A.B., Bauer, T.N., Erdogan, B., Parker, S.K., Tims, M., Zacher, H. with 5 documents.

Source: Scopus data base

Figure 2 Most individual Proactive Personality Literature Researcher

3.3. Nation Number of Annual Publication of Proactive Personality Literature

When it comes to active publication of personality literature, the United States is a leading research nation with 170 scientific treatises. This is followed by 115 documents and 31 documents from China and Australia, 29 documents from Taiwan, 29 documents from the United Kingdom, 22 documents from Hong Kong, 22 documents from the Netherlands, 21 documents from Germany, 20 documents from Canada, and 18 documents from India.

Source: Scopus data base

Figure 3 Number of Documents by Nation from the Proactive Personality Literature

3.4. The Largest Frequency of Publication of Proactive Personality Literature by Subject Area

Majors in business, management and accounting with 293 documents (33.3%) are the most used majors in international research on proactive personality, psychology (26.1%) with 230 documents, social sciences (16.7%) of 147 documents, followed by a decision science 34 documents (3.9%), 33 documents in economics, econometrics and finance (3.8%), 23 documents in computer science (2.6%), 20 documents in medicine (2.3%), art and humanities 19 documents (2.2%), Engineering (2.0%) with 18 documents and Agricultural and Biological Sciences (1.7%) with 15 documents.

Source: Scopus data base

Figure 4 The Largest Frequency of Publication of Proactive Personality by Subject Area

3.5. Year Documents of Proactive Personality Literature Publication Sources

The leader in the annual number of sources of proactive personality publications is the Journal of Vocational behavior with 26 documents, followed by the Journal of Applied Psychology with 20 documents, Social behavior And Personality with 15 documents, Career Development International with 14 documents, and Personality and Individual Differences with 12 documents.

Source: Scopus data base

Figure 5 Year Annual Documents of Proactive Personality Literature Publication Sources

3.6. Annual documents from the Proactive Personality Literature

The variety of annual global guides of the proactive personality literature suggests a growing trend each year. The variety of annual files consistent with year on proactive personality guides is that during 2020 there have been 97 papers, and in 2019 there have been 97 papers.

Source: Scopus data base

Figure 6 Annual Number of Documents per Year from the Proactive Personality Literature

3.7. The Proactive Personality Literature Article Cited

Study by Crant, J.M. is the most cited publication on proactive personality. The most cited number in 2000 was entitled "Proactive behavior in organizations", citing 1140 documents.

3.8. Map of Study Themes

The evaluation and visualization of the VOSViewer program further developed the structure from the topic map of the journal to the proactive personality keyword framework of the proactive personality literature. 5 repetitions are a standard for minimizing diversity in keyword-related documents. Therefore, 115 out of 1,819 key phrases met the threshold. from the figure below, there are seven agencies of booklet topics that depend upon the observe key phrases of worldwide instructional courses of proactive personality literature, which can be simplified and abbreviated as PECOME topics.

Source: Output VOSviewer

Figure 7 Map of Study Themes

Remark:

- Personality cluster (green). The key words age, stress, cognition, physiology, behavioural response is predominantly in this cluster. Many of these keywords relate to personality themes.
- Employee cluster (red). Keywords: proactive personality, leadership, performance, employee creativity, core self-evaluations, dominate this cluster.
- Career cluster (Yellow). The keywords career, human experiment, controlled study, and trust dominate this cluster. Many of these keywords are linked to career themes.
- Organization cluster (blue). Keywords: organization culture, job satisfaction, motivation, human relations, personality inventory, are dominated in this cluster. Many of these keywords are related to organizational themes.
- Manager cluster (Purple). The keywords managers and mentoring are dominated in this cluster.
- Entrepreneur cluster (light blue). The keywords entrepreneurial intentions, creativity, and self-efficacy dominate this cluster.

3.9. Network of Authorship

With the VOSViewer program, constructs had been advanced on a proactive personality researcher framework for authorship community maps. Five files are one of the minimal necessities for a eBook series consistent with author. So, out of 1,229 researchers, 14 researchers who reached the brink had been recognized. As proven in below Figure, there's a community of institution partnerships among worldwide researchers within side the eBook of the proactive personality literature. The proactive personality red cluster contains: Wang, Z. Li, M., and Liu, Y.

Source: Output VOSviewer

Figure 7 Authorship Network Map

3.10. Managerial Implication

In phrases of the results of contributing expertise, this have a look at recommends a convergence axis category which includes courses within side the proactive personality literature to categorize our bodies of expertise made from thirty-six years of instructional courses: Personality, Employee, Career, Organization, Manager, and Entrepreneur, abbreviated as PECOME subject matters. The identity of key subject matters in proactive personality, as realistic implications, contributes to the attention of the advent of realistic research to make clear contexts and widespread topics, in addition to studies gaps. All of this may result in new studies that addresses a loss of have a look at and particular information in scientific disciplines. The maximum studied subject matters regularly replicate the capacity to make a contribution proactive persona to the corporation environment, technology, and management.

4. Conclusion

As a result, we found that the number of international publications on "proactive personality" such as maps and visual patterns is increasing year by year. In publishing proactive personality publications, Renmin University of China Research is the most active research institute with 12 articles. On the other hand, Crant, J.M. 11 articles an individual academic researcher with the most prolific publications in the publication of the proactive personality literature. country that has contributed the most. With 293 documents (33.3%), business, management, and accounting were the most publication-intensive research areas in the publication of proactive personality literature. The Journal of Vocational Behavior, a literature publication on proactive personality, is a large body of annual documents containing 26 documents according to sources. With 97 articles, it is the world's best of scholarly publications in proactive personality literature 2020. The work of Crant, J.M. most of them are the most cited publications. In 2008, it cites 1,140 documents entitled "Proactive behavior in organizations". There is one group of research partnerships associated with the publication of the proactive personality literature.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The Authors wish to declare that none has any interest to disclose.

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